

Title: Transforming the Video Ecosystem with Blockchain

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INTRODUCTION:

As the web becomes increasingly cluttered with out of touch content, invalid traffic and pointless attention-based metrics, advertisers, content creators and publishers struggle to find the proper way to reach consumers. Sensory and content overload make it almost impossible to captivate and monetize audiences looking for targeted experiences.

AIM:

The Interactive Video and Experience Protocol (IVEP)'s programmable smart and adaptive objects and functions will augment and transform "static" video experiences (legacy) on existing video platforms into powerful and dynamic live engaging systems (next generation). These systems will offer rich interactive and relevant experiences, capture real human engagement and measure performance in a better and more transparent manner.

KEYWORDS:

Blockchain, video advertising, marketing, content

BIOGRAPHY:

Fred is the founder and CEO of the Interactive Video and Experience Protocol (IVEP). He is a versatile technology entrepreneur, lawyer, inventor, and former platoon commander, with an intuitive market vision, and strengths in various tech stacks, business, corporate law, and finance.

Before founding dubdub.com, Fred practiced law in the areas of financing, technology, intellectual property, securities and mergers, and acquisitions at Stikeman Elliott and Osler. He is also the Founding Partner at blue HF, a boutique business law firm in Montréal which specializes in corporate, commercial and transactional legal services to VCs, SMEs and startup companies, with a focus on software technologies.

